

Exploring the Z-score Metrics in Determining the Financial Soundness of Insurance Firms in Nigeria

BAMGBOSE, Olalekan S^{1*} DALLAH, Hamadu² ADELEKE, Ismaila A.³

¹ Department of Actuarial Science and Insurance, Lagos State University of Science and Technology, Lagos, Nigeria. ORCID ID: 0009000110469721

² Department of Actuarial Science and Insurance, University of Lagos, Akoka, Yaba, Lagos, Nigeria.

³ Department of Actuarial Science and Insurance, University of Lagos, Akoka, Yaba, Lagos, Nigeria.

Emails: ¹ sodiq.bamgbose1976@gmail.com*, dallaram2014@gmail.com

Corresponding Author: BAMGBOSE, Olalekan S^{1}

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ABSTRACT

The Z-score measure, which has traditionally been used as a proxy of individual risk in the banking sector, maybe a useful tool when applied in the insurance sector. This paper compares six different Z-score approaches to examine which one best fits insurance company. The study uses a final data set of 83 firms (listed and unlisted) operating in the Nigeria insurance sector during the period 2015–2022. The study, started by using a root mean squared error (RMSE) criterion to evaluate which of the various mean and standard deviation (SD) estimates that are used to compute the Z-score that best fits the data. The study employed the use of an ordinary least squares (OLS) regression model to estimate and compare the explanatory variables of the six Z-score measures. The study revealed that the best formula for calculating the Z-score of insurance firms is the one that combines the current value of the return on assets (ROA) and capitalization with the standard deviation (SD) of the returns calculated over the full sample period. The study recommended the use of Z-score measure by regulatory supervisors and other relevant stakeholders as a useful early warning indicator of financial distress.

Keywords: Z-score, Insurance Sector, Economic Crisis, Financial Soundness, Nigeria Financial System.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

The insurance industry plays a crucial role in the economy by allowing individuals and companies to transfer risk through insurance and reinsurance activities thereby enhancing financial stability (Alhassan. & Biekpe, 2022). Haiss and Sumegi, (2022) argues that, the insurance has become an important pillar of the financial sector through its significant contribution to the economic growth. Caporale et al., (2017) argued that insurance companies have traditionally been considered less risky than banks because they are less exposed to liquidity risk .the increasing interactions among the insurance sector, financial markets and other financial intermediaries, as

well as financial innovations, globalization and the deregulation of the financial system, have made the operations of financial intermediaries over the last decades more complex and potentially riskier (Sharpe & Stadnik, 2017). While the contagion effects from the failure of firms in the insurance sector may not be as consequential as those in the banking industry, they have relevant potential to disrupt the financial system and negatively impact the economy (Laeven & Levine, 2019a). Therefore, the soundness of insurance firms is of major importance not only for the welfare of the financial sector and various stakeholders, but also for the stability of the economy as a whole (Pasiouras & Gaganis, 2023).

Consequent upon this, insolvency reduction and low confidence in the insurance sector are being focused on by policy makers through the upgrading of regulatory and supervisory framework. In the light of this, the insurance sector has adopted solvency requirements risk-based economic approach called the IFRS 17, for better reflection of companies' risk (Altuntas, & Rauch, 2017). The IFRS 17 is based on prospective calculations that ensure accurate and timely interventions by the regulatory and supervisory authority. The need for less complex indicators of the soundness of insurers other than the IFRS 17, should however be considered by financial soundness reporters. The popularity of the Z-score derives from its relative simplicity and the fact that it can be computed using accounting information alone. In contrast to market-based risk measures, this indicator is applicable when dealing with an extensive number of unlisted as well as listed companies (Chiaramonte et al., 2016).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

A broad strand of the literature has focused on the analysis of diverse measures of capitalization (i.e. the actual solvency margin, the required solvency margin, or the solvency ratio) to draw conclusions about the financial soundness of firms (Cummins & Nini, 2002; De Haan & Kakes, 2010; Rubio-Misas & Fernandez-Moreno, 2017; Moreno et al., 2020). Nevertheless, limiting the analysis to insurers' capitalization could be too restrictive, and a wider approach is necessary to examine the different factors that influence the financial soundness of an insurer (Hu & Yu, 2014; Mankai & Belgacem, 2016; Altuntas & Rauch, 2017; Cummins et al., 2017; Shim, 2017). The Z-score can be considered an alternative measure of risk and thus a good indicator of the financial soundness of insurers that takes into account factors beyond capitalization or the particular event of bankruptcy (Caporale et al., 2017).

1.3 Objective

Precisely the objective of this paper is to examining and comparing different approaches to calculating the Z-score on a sample of insurance firms. The few available results on the predictive power of this indicator are mixed and focus on the banking sector.

1.4 Hypotheses of the Study

The Z-score can be considered an alternative measure of risk and thus a good indicator of the financial soundness of insurers that takes into account factors beyond capitalization or the particular event of bankruptcy.

$$Zs1_t = \frac{ROA_t + Eq/TA_t}{(\sigma ROA)_3 (ROA_t, ROA_{t-1}, ROA_{t-2})} \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Zs1 is not the best metrics to be used in considering the financial soundness of insurers that takes into account factors beyond capitalization or the particular event of bankruptcy.

Delis and Staikouras (2011) and Baselga-Pascual et al. (2015) derive a Z-score measure (Zs2) that uses data from the two previous years to calculate σROA at time t (σROA_2):

$$Zs2_t = \frac{ROA_t + Eq/TA}{\sigma ROA_2 (ROA_{t-1}, ROA_{t-2})} \text{-----(ii)}$$

Hypothesis 2 (H2): Zs2 is not the best metrics to be used in considering the financial soundness of insurers that takes into account factors beyond capitalization or the particular event of bankruptcy.

Maechler et al. (2010) and Chiaramonte et al. (2016) compute the Z-score as the sum of the three-year moving average of ROA ($ROA_{\mu 3}$) and the three-year moving average of the equity to-total assets ratio ($Eq/TA_{\mu 3}$) divided by σROA_3

$$Zs3_t = \frac{ROA_{\mu 3}(ROA_t, ROA_{t-1}, ROA_{t-2}) + Eq/TA_{\mu 3}(Eq/TA_t, Eq/TA_{t-1}, Eq/TA_{t-2})}{\sigma ROA_3 (ROA_t; ROA_{t-1}; ROA_{t-2})} \text{ (iii)}$$

Hypothesis 3 (H3): Zs3 is not the best metrics to be used in considering the financial soundness of insurers that takes into account factors beyond capitalization or the particular event of bankruptcy.

Yeyati and Micco (2007) compute the Z-scores for each firm and year combining $ROA_{\mu 3}$ with Eq/TA_t and σROA_3 :

$$Zs4_t = \frac{ROA_{\mu 3} (ROA_t; ROA_{t-1}; ROA_{t-2}) + Eq/TA_t}{\sigma ROA_3 (ROA_t; ROA_{t-1}; ROA_{t-2})} \text{----- (iv)}$$

Hypothesis 4 (H4): Zs4 is not the best metrics to be used in considering the financial soundness of insurers that takes into account factors beyond capitalization or the particular event of bankruptcy.

Boyd et al. (2006) and Chiara monte et al. (2016) calculates the Z-score as the sum of ROA_t and $Eq/TA_{\mu 3}$ divided by σROA_3 :

$$Zs5_t = \frac{ROA_t (Eq/TA_{\mu 3} (Eq/TA_t; Eq/TA_{t-1}; Eq/TA_{t-2}))}{\sigma ROA_3 (ROA_t; ROA_{t-1}; ROA_{t-2})} \text{----- (v)}$$

Hypothesis 5 (H5): Zs5 is not the best metrics to be used in considering the financial soundness of insurers that takes into account factors beyond capitalization or the particular event of bankruptcy.

A Z-score measure can also estimate the combination of ROA_t and Eq/TA_t with the SD of ROA calculated over the full period (σROA_T) (Beck & Laven, 2006 ; Hesse & Cihak, 2007):

$$Zs6_t = \frac{ROA_t (Eq/TA_t)}{\sigma ROA_T (ROA_1; ROA_2; \dots; ROA_T)} \text{----- (vi)}$$

Hypothesis 6 (H6): Zs6 is not the best metrics to be used in considering the financial soundness of insurers that takes into account factors beyond capitalization or the particular event of bankruptcy.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Explanations

2.1 Conceptual Explanation

The insurance sector through its significant contribution to economic growth has become an important pillar of the financial sector (Haiss & Sumegi, 2008). Therefore, the financial soundness of insurance firms is of major importance not only for the welfare of the financial sector and various stakeholders (Pasiouras & Gaganis, 2013) but also for the stability of the economy as a whole.

Consequent upon this, regulator, policy holders, and other stakeholders need to have good knowledge of the financial soundness of an insurer. The use of a less complex simplified method that requires simple accounting knowledge will be appreciated. Z-score metric provide the simplicity in computation.

The Altman Z-score is a method that combines quantitative financial indicators with a limited number of variables to forecast if a company would fail financially or enter bankruptcy. According to Altman (1968), Z-score can accurately predict failure up to two years in advance. This model can be applied to predict bankruptcy by organization stakeholders as well as outsiders and the potential stakeholders (Strebros et al., 2021). This measure can be applied to insurers with different risk strategies (Cihak & Hesse, 2010; Pasiouras & Gaganis, 2013): an institution may have the same or higher Z-score than other insurers with lower capitalization if it has higher risk-adjusted returns

The basic principle behind the Z-score is to relate the capital ratio to the variability in the ROA so that one can know how much variability in returns can be absorbed by capital without the firm becoming insolvent (Li et al., 2017):

$$Z\text{-score (Zs)} = \frac{ROA}{\sigma ROA} + \frac{Eq/TA}{\sigma ROA} \text{----- (i)}$$

Where ROA = Return on Assets,
Eq/TA = Equity -to- Total Assets ratio
σROA = Standard Deviation of Return -on -assets

Default is expected to occur when losses consume capital (i.e. when $ROA \leq - Eq/TA$). Then, if we assume that ROA is a random variable, the Z-score represents the number of standard deviations between the expected value of the ROA, $E(ROA)$ and the negative values of ROA, $ROA = - Eq/TA$, that would result in insolvency (Hannan & Hanweck, 1988). In other words, it indicates the number of standard deviations that the ROA would have to fall to deplete equity and force a failure. As in the banking sector, equity serves as a buffer against unforeseen losses and is critical for an insurer’s ability to meet its obligations (Cummins et al., 2017). Hannan and Hanweck (1988) show that the Chebyshev inequality for any symmetric distribution allows us to assume the following upper bound on the probability of default (PD):

$$PD \leq \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\sigma ROA}{E(ROA) + Eq/TA} \cdot 2 \right]^2 = \frac{1}{2} (Zs)^{-2} \text{----- (ii)}$$

2.2 Theoretical Framework

There are several theories that fit into the study. However, our study adopts the Theory of Financial Distress and Bankruptcy Prediction, Information Asymmetry Theory and Risk- Based Capital (RBC) Theory.

2.2.1 Theory of Financial Distress and Bankruptcy Prediction

This study is primarily grounded in the Financial Distress Theory, which explains the condition under-which a firm becomes unable to meet its financial obligations. Financial distress occurs when an organization experiences declining earnings, liquidity shortage, and determining asset quality. Insurance companies are particularly vulnerable due to long-term liability structure,

uncertainty in claims occurrence and investment risk. The Z-score models serves as early warning indications of distress by combining financial ratios into a single predictive metric.

2.2.2 Risk-Based Capital Theory

The study also draws from this theory, which emphasizes that an insurer's solvency depends on the adequacy of capital relative to risk exposure. The insurance risk includes; underwriting risk, market risk, credit risk and operational risk. The Z-score models indirectly capture these risk through financial ratios such as leverage, profitability, and liquidity

2.2.3 Information Asymmetry Theory

This theory highlights that stakeholders (policyholders, regulators, investors) lack full information about insurers' financial health. The Z-score models reduce the gap by providing a standardized solvency indicator and transparency enhancement.

2.3 Empirical Review of Study

A broad strand of the literature has focused on the analysis of diverse measures of capitalization (i.e. the actual solvency margin, the required solvency margin, or the solvency ratio) to draw conclusions about the financial soundness of firms (Cummins & Nini, 2002; De Haan & Kakes, 2010; Rubio-Misas & Fernandez-Moreno, 2017; Moreno et al., 2020). The Z-score may be a simple and effective predictor of insurer failure given the simplicity and transparency of its calculation (Plantin & Rochet, 2007) and because it can be computed for both unlisted and listed firms (Bongini et al., 2018). Altman's model achieved high accuracy level in predicting the bankruptcy of Singapore retail companies (Muzani & Yuliana, 2021). Z-score model was found to accurately predict business bankruptcy for textile companies in Pakistan (Hussain et al., 2014). In case of Greek companies, Altman model performed well at foreseeing failure up to five years in advance (Alexakis, 2008).

In the same vein, Bongini et al. (2018) conclude that the Z-score has limitations in the macro prudential monitoring framework for detecting banking crises, at least in emerging economies, because accounting-based measures do not capture all of the dimensions of risk, such as contagion and interconnectedness (i.e. systemic risk). Some recent studies have used this measure to examine the financial soundness of insurance firms (Shim, 2011; Pasiouras & Gaganis, 2013; Altuntas & Rauch, 2021; Shim, 2017; Alhassan & Biekpe, 2018; Gaganis et al., 2019, Pavic et al., 2019; Rubio-Misas, 2020). The most basic formulation defines the Z-score as the sum of the values in the current period t of the firm's ROA (ROA_t) and equity-to-total assets ratio (Eq/TA_t) divided by the SD of ROA calculated with data from the current year (t) and the two previous years, i.e. $t-1$ and $t-2$ (σROA_3) (Pasiouras & Gaganis, 2013; Chiaramonte et al., 2016; Cummins et al., 2017). From these array of studies, there is hardly any existing that investigated the financial soundness of a firm using different Z-score models. This is the main aim of this study.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

A Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) criterion was used to evaluate which of the various mean and SD estimates that are used to compute the Z-score best fits the data.

3.2 Population of the Study

Finally, we remove observations with abnormal ratios or extreme values from the sample, ensuring that the analysis is not affected by potential measurement error or misreporting. After applying these filters, we obtain a final dataset consisting of an unbalanced panel with 83 insurers (listed and unlisted). 1,382 observations were made.

3.3 Instrumentation

A system-GMM estimator developed by Arellano and Bover (1995) and Blundell and Bond (1998) was used for dynamic panel data models.

3.4 Validity of Research Instrument

We verify the validity of the instruments by using Hansen's J-test of over identifying restrictions. The higher values of the lagged dependent variables confirm the dynamic character of the model specification, indicating strong persistence; i.e. the adjustment of risk is very slow. As expected, the regression coefficients indicate a positive relationship between size and the Z-score; i.e. larger firms are less risky than smaller firms, supporting previous findings in the literature (Chen & Wong, 2004; Pasiouras & Gaganis, 2013; Shim, 2017).

3.5 Reliability of Research Instrument

Basically, the essence of the unit root test is to justify the reliability of data and the results of the analysis. All the variables in this study were stationary at level and order; one as all the probability values were significant at 1, 5 and 10%. Categorically, INP, which is the dependent variable, was stationary at order 1 and this justifies the test of co-integration among the variables. This result is in line with the postulation of Pesaran et al. (2001), hence the use of an ordinary least square model.

3.6 Method of Data Collection

The study sample includes most of the insurance companies operating in Nigeria from 2015–2022. Data were obtained from the data base maintained by the Nigerian insurance regulatory authority, the National Insurance Commission (NAICOM), the Nigerian stock exchange (NSE) digest The study, do not consider reinsurance specialists because of their linearity in characteristics that may distort our analysis. In order to minimize the possibility of aggregation, unconsolidated financial statements were used for the study.

3.7 Method of Data Analysis

The Study estimate and compare the explanatory power of the six Z-score measures that are considered by using an ordinary least squares (OLS) regression model. Root -Mean Square Error., and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF).

3.8 Ethical Considerations

Confidential and anonymity were strictly maintained. The research was designed to avoid any form of arm. Transparency and honesty were upheld in the analysis and reporting of findings, with no form of data manipulation. The study was conducted without any conflict of interest and strictly for academic purposes in line with ethical research principles.

3.9 Limitation of the Methodology

The use of sample data from the data base of NAICOM, increases the reliance on secondary data, where cases of approximations and error in calculations might have occurred.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

4.1 Analysis of Results

4.1.1 Analyzing Z-score Metrics

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of different Z-score metrics

Full sample	Zs1	Zs2	Zs3	Zs4	Zs5	Zs6
Mean	3.787	4.232	3.772	3.780	3.693	3.085
SD	1.290	1.594	1.294	1.307	1.268	0.995
Min	-2.642	-1.967	-2.759	-1.967	-0.389	-2.843
Max	9.817	11.927	9.833	9.817	9.825	8.168
Nonlife Insurers						
Mean	3.786	4.200	3.768	3.776	3.651	3.059
SD	1.277	1.548	1.295	1.303	1.334	1.143
Life Insurers						
Mean	3.790	4.319	3.781	3.789	3.708	3.095
SD	1.323	1.710	1.306	1.320	1.243	0.933
2015						
Mean	3.585	4.004	3.610	3.598	3.521	3.007
SD	1.342	1.662	1.246	1.274	1.233	1.070
2016						
Mean	3.791	4.235	3.794	3.781	3.707	3.032
SD	1.311	1.588	1.302	1.340	1.283	0.972
2017						
Mean	3.759	4.258	3.731	3.754	3.659	3.055
SD	1.392	1.748	1.391	1.399	1.330	1.009
2018						
Mean	3.751	4.277	3.696	3.724	3.614	3.108
SD	1.197	1.444	1.244	1.228	1.229	0.926
2019						
Mean	3.772	4.077	3.753	3.766	3.670	3.116
SD	1.197	1.498	1.191	1.214	1.180	0.999
2020						
Mean	3.768	4.226	3.758	3.766	3.680	3.110
SD	1.197	1.498	1.191	1.214	1.180	0.999
2021						
Mean	3.939	4.352	3.929	3.933	3.854	3.131
SD	1.262	1.585	1.267	1.282	1.248	1.017
2022						
Mean	3.975	4.481	3.946	3.957	3.882	3.136
SD	1.282	1.532	1.375	1.323	1.309	1.002

Source: Researchers' computation, (2026)

Table 2 reports some descriptive statistics for the six different time-varying Z-score measures. The Mean results as calculated per insurer, for Zs1, Zs3, Zs4 and Zs5 are very similar, in the interval of 3.693–3.787. Zs2 presents a higher mean and Standard deviation (SD). Zs6, on the

other hand, has results that are very different from those of the other measures, with average means and standard deviations in a lower range as well as a smaller average coefficient of variation (0.320). Similarly, we find differences in these measures between life and non-life specialized insurers. Finally, the lowest average Z-score is reported in 2015, whereas the highest Z-score mean values are found in 2021 and 2022, which is in line with the improvements in the Nigeria economy after the Covid 19 pandemic.

Table 2: Correlation Coefficient of different Zs scores

	Zs1	Zs2	Zs3	Zs4	Zs5	Zs6
Zs1	1					
Zs2	0.7853***	1				
Zs3	0.9863***	0.7756***	1			
Zs4	0.9943***	0.7825***	0.9928***	1		
Zs5	0.9821***	0.7688***	0.9910***	0.9841***	1	
Zs6	0.6885***	0.5398***	0.6711***	0.6831***	0.6609***	1

Source: Researchers' Computation, (2026)

Table 3 presents the average correlation coefficients of our six different Z-score measures: Zs1, Zs3, Zs4 and Zs5 have correlation coefficients close to 1, the coefficients for Zs2 and Zs6 are however much lower. This result shows the financial soundness of insurance firms in Nigeria.

Table 3: Comparative analysis of Zs scores with explanatory variables

Variables	Zs1	Zs2	Zs3	Zs4	Zs5	Zs6
Size	0.153*** (0.039)	0.157*** (0.044)	0.139*** (0.039)	0.155*** (0.040)	0.128*** (0.038)	0.145*** (0.039)
Capitalization	2.697*** (0.415)	2.716*** (0.429)	2.635*** (0.420)	2.743*** (0.424)	2.691*** (0.409)	2.819*** (0.380)
Profitability	3.388** (1.661)	3.906** (1.661)	2.642 (1.813)	3.213* (1.764)	0.189 (1.436)	3.982*** (1.339)
Reinsurance	-0.198 (0.299)	-0.086 (0.297)	-0.234 (0.311)	-0.238 (0.315)	-0.214 (0.297)	0.345 (0.277)
Portfolio risk	0.641 (0.490)	0.391 (0.553)	0.691 (0.476)	0.636 (0.495)	0.676 (0.470)	0.574 (0.427)
Underwriting risk	-0.116 0.221*** (0.123)	-0.079 (0.131)	-0.140 (0.129)	-0.126 (0.129)	-0.128 (0.124)	- (0.127)
Life Insurance	0.680*** (0.206)	0.699*** (0.214)	0.691*** (0.211)	0.693*** (0.210)	0.613*** (0.208)	0.719*** (0.206)
Concentration	-0.001 0.000	-0.003	0.000	0.000	0.000	-

	(0.002)	(0.003)	(0.002)	(0.002)	(0.002)	(0.000)
Constant	- 0.046	1.192	-0.412	-0.452	-0.128	-
1.123						
Year Dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Number of firms	83	83	83	83	83	83
Number of observations	1,382	1,382	1,382	1,382	1,382	1,382
R ²	19.47%	12.99%	18.23%	19.33%	18.64%	32.60%
Adjusted R ²	18.53%	11.97%	17.27%	18.38%	17.69%	31.81%
F-Value	7.97	6.85	8.02	8.16	9.06	12.41

Source: Researchers' Computation, (2026)

Table 4, we estimate and compare the explanatory power of the six Z-score measures considered. The regression model that uses Zs6 presents the highest explanatory power, with values for the adjusted R² slightly higher than 30%. The rest of the models exhibit values close to 20%, except for Zs2, for which the adjusted R² falls to 12%. Therefore, we confirm that the Zs6 model is the best option for explaining insurer risk, in accordance with the results reported by the RMSE criterion. Significance levels are indicated as follows: ***5 significance at the 1 percent level, **5 significance at the 5 percent level, and *5 significance at the 10 percent level

4.1 Determining the Z-score that best fit the data

Following a procedure similar to that employed by Lepetit and Strobel (2013) for the banking sector, we opt for a root mean squared error (RMSE) criterion to evaluate which estimator best fits the data by minimizing the weighted average RMSE of the N insurers j given by

$$RMSE = \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{T_j}{\sum_{j=1}^N T_j} \sqrt{\frac{1}{T_j} \sum_{t=1}^{T_j} [x_{jt} - e^{-i\omega t}]^2}$$

The RMSE is the square root of the mean of the squares of all of the errors, and it is considered to be an excellent error metric for numerical predictions.

Table 4: Root Mean Square Error for the components of the different Z-score approaches

Z-scores	ROA _t	ROA _{μ3}	Eq/TA _t	Eq/TA _{μ3}	σROA ₂	σROA ₃	σROA _T
Zs1	[1.2781]		[1.2423]			[1.0464]	
Zs2	[1.5843]		[1.5630]		[1.3402]		
Zs3		[1.2702]		[1.2530]		[1.0219]	
Zs4		[1.2775]	[1.2599]			[1.0297]	
Zs5	[1.2682]			[1.2134]		[1.0484]	
Zs6	[0.9729]		[0.9174]				[0.8203]

Table1 shows the results of the weighted average RMSE for each of the components of the Z-scores considered in the current study (i.e. Zs1–Zs6), indicating that Zs6 is the Z-score measure that best fits the data. Therefore, according to this criterion, the best way to calculate the Z-score

is using the values of ROA and Eq/TA in current period t together with the SD of ROA calculated over the full sample (Beck & Laeven 2006; Hesse & Cihak 2007)

4.2 Analyzing the Determinant of Insurers Risk

Table 5: Determinant of Insurers Risk in Nigeria

Variables	Zs1	Zs2	Zs3	Zs4	Zs5	Zs6
Sizes	0.153*** (0.039)	0.157*** (0.044)	0.139*** (0.039)	0.155*** (0.040)	0.128*** (0.038)	0.145*** (0.039)
Profitability	3.388** (1.661)	3.906** (1.661)	2.642 (1.813)	3.213* (1.764)	0.189 (1.436)	3.982*** (1.339)
Capitalization	2.697*** (0.415)	2.716*** (0.429)	2.635*** (0.420)	2.743*** (0.424)	2.691*** (0.409)	2.819*** (0.380)
Reinsurance	-0.198 (0.299)	-0.086 (0.297)	-0.234 (0.311)	-0.238 (0.315)	-0.214 (0.297)	0.345 (0.277)
Portfolio risk	0.641 (0.490)	0.391 (0.553)	0.691 (0.476)	0.636 (0.495)	0.676 (0.470)	0.574 (0.427)
Underwriting risk	-0.116 (0.123)	-0.079 (0.131)	-0.140 (0.129)	-0.126 (0.129)	-0.128 (0.124)	- (0.127)
Life insurance	0.680*** (0.206)	0.699*** (0.214)	0.691*** (0.211)	0.693*** (0.210)	0.613*** (0.208)	0.719*** (0.206)
Concentration	-0.001 (0.002)	-0.003 (0.003)	0.000 (0.002)	0.000 (0.002)	0.000 (0.002)	-0.000 (0.000)
Year Dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Number of observations	1,382	1,382	1,382	1,382	1,382	1,382
Number of Firms	183	183	183	183	183	183
R²	19.47%	12.99%	18.23%	19.33%	18.64%	32.60%
Adjusted R²	18.53%	11.97%	17.27%	18.38%	17.69%	31.81%
F-value	7.97 (16,182)	6.85 (16,182)	8.02 (16,182)	8.16 (16,182)	9.06 (16,182)	12.41 (16,182)

Source: Researchers' Computation, (2026)

Table 6: Variance Inflation Factors

Variables	VIF
Industry Concentration	6.010
Year 2017	3.870
Year 2018	3.200
Capitalization	3.010
Sizes	2.480
Life Insurance	2.070
Long-Tailed Business	1.830
Year 2019	1.740
Year 2020	1.560
Year 2021	1.370
Year 2022	1.360
Underwriting Risk	1.230
Reinsurance	1.170
Portfolio Risk	1.150
Profitability	1.110
Mean VIF	2.150

Some specific factors that influence insurer risk may be endogenous (e.g. insurers might need to increase their capital ratio if they become riskier) and others are difficult to measure or identify in an equation (e.g. managerial ability), in Table 2, we report the results of our baseline equation using the system-GMM estimator developed by Arellano and Bover (1995) and Blundell and Bond (1998) for dynamic panel data models. The persistence of risk has been well documented in the banking literature (Baselga-Pascual et al., 2015). The study uses the system-GMM method because of availability of information on all of the analyzed variables for at least five consecutive years for each insurer. A two –step estimation procedure with quantified sample corrected errors as proposed by Windmeijer (2005) was employ by the study. This method provides a less biased coefficient estimates and more accurate standard errors.

5. Discussion of Findings

We treat insurer characteristics (except their organizational form and their specialization) as endogenous variables by using suitable instruments for both the equation in levels and the equation indifferences. Industry concentration and macro -economic control variables (year dummies) are considered strictly exogenous. We verify the validity of the instruments by using Hansen’sJ-test of over identifying restrictions. The higher values of the lagged dependent variables (except for the Zs2 regression) confirm the dynamic character of the model specification, indicating strong persistence; i.e. the adjustment of risk is very slow.

As expected, the regression coefficients indicate a positive relationship between size and the Z-score; i.e. larger firms are less risky than smaller firms, supporting previous findings in the literature (Chen & Wong, 2004; Pasiouras & Gaganis, 2013; Shim, 2017). We demonstrate a strong positive relationship between ROA and the Z-score but only when Zs6 is used as the dependent variable. This result supports the hypothesis that highly profitable insurers are less likely to become insolvent because they manage expenses effectively and can set competitive premium rates (Caporale et al., 2017). The relationship with capitalization, as measured by the equity-to total assets ratio, is positive and statistically significant in all of the analyzed models.

This finding corroborates the hypothesis that more capitalized insurers have higher Z-scores (Shim, 2011; Altuntas & Rauch, 2017). We also report that a greater use of reinsurance may increase the financial soundness of firms; i.e. higher levels of reinsurance result in lower insurer risk by transferring part of this risk to third parties (Alhassan & Biekpe, 2018). However, this result applies only to the Zs6 approach and has low statistical significance. The positive coefficient we find for the dummy that identifies mutual insurance companies is in accordance with the hypothesis that mutual companies are more financially stable than stock insurers because in mutual companies, the policyholders are also the owners of the firms. Therefore, managers' incentives to increase asset risk are lower in mutual companies than in stock firms (Shim, 2017). Similar to Pasiouras and Gaganis (2013), we also find a positive coefficient for the dummy that identifies life insurance companies, corroborating the hypothesis that life insurers are more financially stable than non-life insurance companies, which may operate as 'risk takers'. The relationship between industrial concentration and the Z-score is negative and significant only for the Zs6 approach.

This result supports the concentration-fragility view, providing empirical evidence against the tendency toward increasing concentration that the Nigeria insurance market is currently experiencing. Finally, we do not find statistical significance for the variables that measure portfolio risk, underwriting risk or whether a business is long-tailed in any of the six models considered. Once again, we observe that the Z-score measure that incorporates the most statistically significant variables in the risk model is the one that combines the current values of ROA and capitalization with the SD of ROA calculated over the full period.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The Z-score can be considered an appropriate alternative measure of risk and thus a good indicator of the financial soundness of insurance firms. This measure relates the insurer's capital level to variability in its returns, revealing how much variability in returns can be absorbed by capital without the firm becoming insolvent. Higher Z-scores indicates a higher solvency and liquidity ratio and thus greater financial soundness. By comparing six different approaches to calculating the Z-score with a final dataset of 183 insurers (listed and unlisted) operating in the Nigeria insurance sector during the period 2015–2022, the study conclude that, the Z-score that combines current ROA and capitalization values with the standard deviation (SD) of ROA over the full period is the most suitable measure for calculating Z-score. This approach (i.e. Zs6) has the advantage of enabling the construction of time-varying Z-scores that do not require initial observations to be dropped

5.2 Recommendations

The Z-score may be a useful early warning indicator for micro prudential supervision. In addition to being an indicator of the soundness of insurers simpler than those established in the current

regulation, the information provided by this accounting-based measure may help analysts and investors obtain a better understanding of insurance firms' risk factors. It is therefore recommended that the Z-score model be used for internal financial supervision use by insurance companies in Nigeria.

5.3 Implication of the Study (Theoretical, Practical, Managerial and Policy Implications)

The Z-score may be a useful early warning indicator for micro-prudential supervision. In addition to being an indicator of the soundness of insurers simpler than those established in the current regulation, the information provided by this accounting-based measure may help analysts and investors obtain a better understanding of insurance firms' risk factors.

5.4 Limitation of the Study

The main limitation of the research is that it addresses only the Nigeria insurance sector, and consequently, the implications of the findings must be framed in this institutional context. However, the authors think that the results could be extrapolated to other countries.

5.5 Areas/Suggestions for Further Studies

Future research should consider including different countries and analyzing the usefulness of aggregated insurer-level Z-scores for macro-prudential monitoring.

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